

Effects of Job Creation on Security Enhancement in Abuja

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Abstract:- This study explores how permanent and temporary job creation affect Abuja's security. Descriptive survey. The study population included 246 NDE headquarters employees in Abuja. Multiple regression analysis is used to assess the effects of employment creation on security. A simple percentage is used to depict the correlations between the study variables. Permanent job creation and Abuja's security are positively correlated, according to the statistics. Results show a significant association between temporary job development and Abuja's security. The research recommends creating more jobs to improve Abuja's safety. The analysis suggests recruiting additional industries to FCT to create jobs and boost security.

Keywords:- Permanent Job Creation, Temporary Job Creation, Security.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of the last decade, the issue of national security has risen to the forefront of concern for many nations, organizations, and social actors. These groups are on the lookout for novel approaches and methods to combat the numerous non-military dangers to peace and security (Hudson, Kreidenweis & Carpenter, 2013). Individual safety is at the core of what it means to ensure the nation's overall safety. National security is differentiated from the goal of preserving state territories, which was the predominant focus of security policy throughout the nineteenth century and a significant portion of the twentieth century, by its emphasis on protecting individuals (Johns, 2014). People, not their genders or races, are the primary concern of national security.

Indeed, concerns over national security highlight the intricate connections—often disregarded or underrated—that exist between disarmament, respect for social rights, and economic growth (Kubo, 2017). Today, in a world that is becoming more globalized, the conditions that give rise to genocide, civil war, human rights violations, global epidemics, environmental degradation, forced and slave labor, and malnutrition are the conditions that pose the most dangerous threats to national security. These conditions include: (Hudson et al., 2013; Fontanel & Corvaisier-Drouart,

2014). Therefore, the human element of security needs to be incorporated into all of the most recent studies on security. Unemployment is an example of a human factor that influences security.

High unemployment rates are a problem that plagues a significant number of urban areas in emerging countries. Nevertheless, urban centers continue to suffer significant rates of rural-to-urban migration despite the fact that large numbers of metropolitan residents who are capable of working are currently without jobs (Kleinschmidt, 2017). Because of this, many young people without jobs have turned to criminal activity, which endangers the nation's safety.

Insurgency is only appealing when the chances of profit outweigh the advantages of avoiding conflict and concentrating on finding other ways to make money (Obasanjo, 2015). According to this point of view, costs of organizing a rebellion are lower in locations where there is a significant population of young people who are without jobs, where there is a high level of deficiency, or where there is an abundance of resources that are simple to steal (Iwu, 2015). This viewpoint is consistent with the belief that armed conflict can be efficiently managed by the implementation of job creation projects in societies that have a significant number of youngsters who are not already working. If we create a calm environment and provide a variety of different income opportunities, there is a good chance that individual decisions will shift away from those that involve conflict. The creation of skilled jobs, semi-skilled jobs, and unskilled jobs are the various aspects of job creation that have the potential to have a optimistic effect on national security. Permanent job creation and temporary job creation are two additional categories that fall under the umbrella of career creation.

➤ Statement of the Problem

The country has been rocked by severe problems with its internal security, including communal, religious, political, and socio-economic battles. These conflicts have resulted in varied degrees of casualties, including deaths and the relocation of a number of people. For example, in the recent past, Abuja was the site of three separate bombings, which together resulted in the loss of many lives, the destruction of countless properties, and the instillation of terror in a great number of people (Obasanjo, 2015). On the basis of this, there

is an immediate need to revise our national security policy and strategy in order to account for new aspects of the security concerns in Nigeria. The hypothesis that unemployment has a causal relationship with armed conflict is still widely held in academic research; hence, efforts to reduce unemployment by increasing work opportunities will have a beneficial effect on national security if the hypothesis is correct (Ololube, Onyekwere, Kpolovie & Agabi, 2012).

Sadly, the unemployment situation continues to worsen with each passing year. Thousands of graduates are aimlessly walking our streets in search of employment opportunities, but without success. The factors contributing to national security have been researched and analyzed in prior empirical investigations. (Mofol1wawo, 2015; Adegoke, 2015; Nwanbi, 2018). Nevertheless, despite a growing interest in youth unemployment in relation to improved security management, none of these authors have quantitatively evaluated the effect of the form of job creation on security, specifically in terms of permanent and temporary job creation. Despite a recent uptick in the number of terrorist strikes targeting young people, this trend persists. This study will evaluate the implications of the form of employment creation on security in Abuja, focusing on the permanent and temporary aspects of job development. This research is intended to fill the void left by earlier studies. This study aims to determine how the form of job creation affects security in Abuja. The study aims to achieve the following specific goals:

- Determine how long-term job creation in Abuja affects crime rates.
- Investigate the impact of short-term hiring on safety in Abuja.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL UNDERPINNING

This inquiry is founded on signal theory, which is one of numerous competing ideas for clarifying the emergence of new occupations. It is predicated on the idea that taking an entry-level position may convey the wrong impression. Signaling theory (Spence, 1973) is frequently used to describe how information, or signals, regarding an organization's qualities revealed during recruitment efforts may impact candidate attraction to a recruiting organization. As a result, talented employees who are likely to be hired in the future are better off remaining unemployed than taking an entry-level position. It has been found that candidates use the recruiter's personality and demeanor as a barometer for the quality of the company they are applying to work for (Collins & Stevens, 2012; Turban & Cable, 2013). (Turban, Forret, & Hendrickson, 1998). This theory has some validity because it says that businesses can improve their ability to recruit top talent by gaining insight into the criteria that job searchers use to determine which organizations to apply to. This theory also rests on the idea that managers can improve their organization's ability to attract qualified candidates by developing and implementing recruitment activities and processes informed by signaling theory.

➤ *Permanent Job Creation and Security*

The research conducted by Mauno and Ruokolainen (2017) investigates the question of whether or not family support protects enduring and temporary workers in the same manner against the detrimental effects of work-family conflict with regard to job satisfaction and the emotional energy level both at work and at home. In 2009, a total of 1,719 nurses working in Finland took part in this research project. According to the findings, temporary workers who had a high level of work-family support from their coworkers were protected from the adverse impacts that high levels of work-family conflict had on their emotional energy while on the job. In addition, temporary workers who had low work-family support from their coworkers were at a greater risk of job dissatisfaction and diminished emotional energy at home than their permanent colleagues who had high work-family conflict. This was the case even though the permanent workers had the same amount of work-family conflict. Temporary workers who suffer work-family conflict may benefit more from the work-family assistance provided by coworkers than other workers. When designing policies and procedures that are family-friendly, businesses with a high percentage of employees on temporary contracts need to take this into consideration.

Yoon, Kim, Park, and Kim (2017) conducted a study that investigated whether or not there is a correlation between shifts in employment status and suicidal ideation in the working population of South Korea. The author merged the data from the Korean Welfare Panel Study, which is still ongoing, in order to get the most out of the analysis. The author conducted an analysis on 3,793 participants who had permanent jobs at the beginning of the study (2011-2014) and who either: (i) kept their permanent jobs; (ii) became full-time precarious workers; (iii) became part-time precarious workers; or (iv) lost their permanent jobs the following year (2012-2015). A yearly assessment of individuals' suicidal ideation was accomplished by having them answer a few questions. Logistic regression was used to investigate the correlations between changes in work status and suicidal ideation. This was done while taking into account potential confounding factors such lifetime suicidal ideation and depressive symptoms at the beginning of the study. Participants who transitioned into part-time or insecure work were more likely to experience suicidal thoughts than those who maintained their permanent employment status throughout the study. According to the findings of the study, an increase in the number of workers in South Korea who have suicidal thoughts may be associated with a change in their employment status from permanent to insecure employment.

➤ *Temporary Job Creation and Security*

Konrad, Moore, Doherty, and Breward (2013) look into the relationship between a worker's disability and their happiness in the workplace by analyzing data on their job status and the kind of accommodations they receive. Statistics Canada's Participation and Activity Limitation Survey data from 2006 were used to examine the link between being employed, having access to reasonable accommodations in the workplace, and overall happiness. The results

demonstrate that permanent employees who are working at their full capacity report higher levels of life satisfaction and lower levels of perceived disability-related discrimination compared to temporary workers and underemployed permanent employees. These results are consistent with the idea that low-quality work has negative consequences on worker well-being because of inadequate need satisfaction and lower social status. All workers with disabilities reported better levels of well-being when their employers made reasonable accommodations for their conditions, and this trend persisted even after controlling for factors including the workers' status as temporary or underemployed. These results provide credence to the idea that main effect and buffering models of workplace stress can be extended to the prediction of experienced prejudice in the workplace.

To what extent employees' performance is affected by factors including employment instability, loyalty, and rewards was the focus of Anwar, Aslam, and Tariq's (2011) research report (incentives). In the minds of workers, job stability and financial rewards go hand in hand. The results of a correlation analysis reveal that performance is positively related to loyalty and incentives but negatively related to the job insecurity inherent in contract work. Loyalty has a favorable relationship with incentives and a negative relationship with the uncertainty that comes with a contract position. The productivity of the workforce is what puts a company at the top of its field. To keep good workers around, businesses should give them guarantees in their employment and pay them extra for doing a good job.

We used data from 11,000 businesses' hiring and firing records spanning a decade and a half to get these conclusions. Arai and Heyman (2012) present fresh empirical evidence showing that temporary contracts, which make up just around 10% of employment, are responsible for over half of the ebb and flow of jobs and workers. Companies use temporary jobs as a safety net when adjusting their workforce, as seen by the positive correlation between the percentage of temporary contracts and employment growth. It is not cyclical for temporary contracts to involve reassignment of jobs. There is cyclical job reallocation in service industries that rely heavily on temporary workers, whereas permanent jobs in manufacturing are countercyclical.

Grassi (2014) assesses the widespread usage of fixed-term contracts in Spain and its impact on enterprises' through its effect on workers' effort. Under reasonable conditions, he proposes a straightforward analytical setup demonstrating that workers' effort is positively correlated with their belief (for a given level of effort) that employers are open to converting temporary contracts into permanent ones. He employs nonparametric tests of stochastic dominance and parametric panel regression methods to examine this conclusion using data on manufacturing firms from 1991 to 2005. The primary takeaways from this research are that

higher conversion rates are beneficial to a company's efficiency, whereas higher proportions of temporary contracts are detrimental.

Scheel, Rigotti, and Mohr (2013) conducted research into the connection between how an organization treats its diverse staff and how well it fulfills its psychological contract (PC). This research involves 78 companies across seven countries and focuses on performance-related compensation and training programmes for a total of 748 temporary and 1,432 permanent employees in the food manufacturing, retail, and educational sectors. Inconsistency in training distribution was positively associated with PC fulfillment, while incongruence with performance-related compensation was not, according to ranked linear models with polynomials for both HR practices. The personal computers of permanent employees gain more from this discrepancy than those of temporary workers. Recommendations for training incongruity stem from the necessity of customizing such programs to the requirements of the target workforce segment.

The purpose of Bellit's (2015) empirical study was to determine if youth residential independence is hindered by fixed-term contracts. Panel data from EU-SILC is used to estimate models of young adults' decisions to move out of their parents' house. The findings reveal that working temporary jobs has no appreciable detrimental effect on young people's chances of starting their own families. For young people, it appears that the sort of contract they receive from their employers is less important than the fact that they have work at all.

With their 2015 paper, "Temporary Agency Work and the Wage-Setting Process," Beissinger and Baudy hope to improve our theoretical knowledge of how temporary agency work affects wage-setting, trade union rents, firm profitability, and job creation. It is demonstrated that in order to reduce the use of temporary agency workers, trade amalgamations may find it desirable to accept lower wages. Therefore, the availability of agency workers to companies may have an impact on wage setting even in companies that only use regular employees. However, if businesses start using contractors instead of full-time employees, trade unions will file more pay claims on behalf of the (remaining) regular workforce. Therefore, it is possible that the high wage level in high-wage enterprises is not a result of but rather a cause of their heavy reliance on temporary agency labor. While we assume monopoly unions, which provide unions the most bargaining power over wages, corporations' employment of temporary agency labor reduces trade unions' economic rents while potentially increasing company profits. Workers hired on temporary contracts were happier and more satisfied with their jobs than those hired permanently. Thus, permanent workers who felt insecure about their employment reported the lowest levels of job satisfaction.

III. METHODOLOGY

➤ Research Design

This study adopted Cross-sectional surveys design.

➤ Population of the Study and Sampling Techniques

The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) headquarters in Abuja was the location of this study's population, which consisted of all two hundred and forty-six (246) staff members. The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) was selected as the organization to work with because it has been in operation for the past three decades, has been tasked with the responsibility of wealth creation via Training, Resettlement, and cash component as loan packages, and has offices in every state of the federation with a large number of beneficiaries working in a variety of trades all over Nigeria.

The size of the sample, which will consist of everyone working in this office, will be determined later. As a result, a procedure known as census sampling is utilized. On the basis of this information,, 246 copies of the questionnaire were sent. Of these, 154 copies of the questionnaire were returned and were found to be useful.

➤ Data Collection

The participants in the study were asked questions on the topic at hand using a questionnaire so that the researchers could compile their findings. The questionnaire is divided into two parts, labeled A and B respectively. The variables that pertain to the participants' personal information are discussed in Section A. This section is divided into two parts. In Section B, we assess how respondents feel about the impact of employment development on Nigeria's national security, and Section A examines how they feel about the topic overall. In a nutshell, the goal of the questionnaire was to ascertain whether or not the development of jobs is now playing a part in lowering the level of insecurity in Nigeria.

In order to measure the constructs, the research used items that were taken from a variety of other studies and found through literature review. The researcher will validate the items by using subject experts in addition to these items, which have already proven remarkable reliability and validity measures in their individual studies. These aspects address all three aspects, namely safety, long-term and short-term employment opportunities, and permanent job generation. The sections on security were taken from Bonner (2016),

while the sections on the development of permanent jobs and temporary jobs were taken from Brecher and Chen (2010) and Cappellari et al. respectively (2012).

➤ Procedure for Data Analysis and Model specification

The participants in the study were asked questions on the topic at hand using a questionnaire so that the researchers could compile their findings. The questionnaire is divided into two parts, labeled A and B respectively. The variables that pertain to the participants' personal information are discussed in Section A. This section is divided into two parts. In Section B, we assess how respondents feel about the impact of employment development on Nigeria's national security, and Section A examines how they feel about the topic overall. In a nutshell, the goal of the questionnaire was to ascertain whether or not the development of jobs is now playing a part in lowering the level of insecurity in Nigeria.

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$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Where;

Y = Security

X₁ = Permanent Job Creation

X₂ = Temporary Job Creation

β₀ = Constant ((Value of Y when all Vs are zero)

β₁—β₂ = Intercepts of Independent Variables

ε = Standard Error term.

The model assumes that permanent and temporary employment creation have a beneficial effect on security. 1 – 2 > 0 means that a unit increase in independent variables increases insecurity by a unit. Thus, regression was used to forecast variable relationships and quantify each explanatory variable's influence dependent variable.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS OF RESULTS

Variables /Description	Coefficients	T – Value	P – Value	F
Permanent Job Creation	0.301	5.083	0.000	
Temporary Job Creation	0.306	4.029	0.001	
R				0.818
R ²				0.669
Adjusted R ²				0.664
F – Value				127.42
P – Value (Probability of F - Statistics)				0.000
Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)				3.702
Cronbach Alpha Value				0.784
Durbin-Watson				1.773

Source: SPSS 2018

Table 1:- Multiple Regression Statistics Table

The findings of this investigation indicate that model is significant because the F value of 127.42 is high, and the P-value of 0.01 is lower than the 0.05 threshold for statistical significance used in this investigation. As a result, the researcher dismissed all of the null hypotheses while permitting the acceptance of the alternative hypotheses.

The coefficients for the creation of permanent jobs are 0.301, while the coefficients for the creation of temporary jobs are 0.306. All of these results are positive, which indicates that an increase in the magnitude of the independent factors will likewise result in a rise in the magnitude of the dependent variable (security).

This consequence also demonstrates the distinct contribution that each aspect of the nature of employment creation makes to the overall explanation of the variance in safety. Since all of these values have been rescaled to the same unit of measurement so that they can be compared, the beta values in Table 4.2 may be used to determine how much each independent variable contributed to the overall accuracy of the prediction of the dependent variable. According to the statistics of the t-test, all of the beta coefficients of permanent job creation and temporary job creation are significant. This is because their respective P-values are 0.01 for each, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. As a consequence of this, all three of the null hypotheses were shown to be incorrect, while the alternative hypotheses were found to be correct.

➤ Discussion of Findings

The findings demonstrate a robust connection between employment creation's intrinsic characteristics and its long-term stability. Overall, the results demonstrate the significance of the link between the way in which new jobs are created and the issue of safety.

A positive and statistically significant correlation between Permanent Job Creation and safety was found. This supports the conclusion reached by Yoon, Kim, Park, and Kim (2017) that the development of permanent jobs has a substantial, beneficial effect on safety. This finding too demonstrates a favorable and statistically significant correlation between the creation of temporary jobs and increased safety.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research demonstrates that the nature of job development has a significant positive impact on safety. This suggests that both permanent and temporary job creation positively impact security. Therefore, it can be stated that employment development is a crucial aspect of strengthening safety.

It is suggested that the government provide additional jobs in order to enhance the security situation in Abuja. Government should lure more industries to FCT in order to create more jobs and hence increase security. This can be accomplished by constructing free trade zones in FCT, providing tax breaks for businesses, and creating a more investment-friendly climate. The only source of data utilized for this investigation was FCT. In future research, a bigger data collection from Nigeria as a whole should be studied.

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